

Welcome to the 3rd volume of the EU-HIP Newsletter!

We are welcoming you to the third edition of our Newsletter. After a warm and productive summer it is time to step into autumn with new activities on the horizon. We will invite you to join us at the second EU-HIP Symposium in Rome, update you with activities which have or will be done and much more. As always, we will introduce you to another project co-funded by the EU which is interesting to follow.

Let's dive into this volume!

Upcoming EU-HIP Symposium in Rome

Co-organized by the Ministry of Health of Italy and Statens Serum Institute of Denmark, with the contribution of all EU-HIP partners, the 2024 EU-HIP Symposium will provide an opportunity to discuss the progress and sustainability of the EU-HIP Project. Following the highly productive 2023 EU-HIP Symposium in Zagreb, this will be the second meeting, aimed at supporting the participating countries in improving their national IT systems to ensure future interoperability with HERA's IT platform. The symposium will also address the state and needs of IT systems in partnering countries and their development.

The 2024 EU-HIP Symposium will present an opportunity for further collaboration with and between the EU-HIP project and the development of the ATHINA platform for assessment of health threats and intelligence gathering of serious cross-border health emergencies and what it means for European countries.

2nd EU-HIP Symposium

October 22nd and 23rd

Palazzo Wedekind, P.za Colonna 366, Rome

Online participation will be available, but interaction will be limited to selected sessions. A detailed agenda will be provided later, with agenda points aligning with the topics mentioned above. In order to participate at the Symposium in-person, please fill in the registration form. Hurry up because registrations are limited and we accept them until October 6th!

We are looking forward to seeing you in Rome!

[REGISTER HERE!](#)

Landscape Analysis - where are we heading next?

Getting deeper insight
around Europe

With the aim to better understand IT systems in place, national legislation, key stakeholders and plans for the future, our team is organising country visits. Members of our team interview experts in the fields of antimicrobial resistance, pathogens of high pandemic potential, medical countermeasures and stockpiling as well as chemical, radiological and nuclear threats on national level. The result of each visit is a detailed report which enables policy and decision makers, public health professionals and other interested parties to get information of interest at a glance.

We are excited to inform you that our team has been active in the past months by visiting Denmark, Iceland and Lithuania. Reports will be made soon and you will get the chance to dive into each country in the following volumes of the Newsletter!

Medical Informatics Europe (MIE) is an annual conference organized by the European Federation of Medical Informatics (EFMI) - gathering healthcare professionals, researchers, and informatics experts from across Europe and beyond. This year the conference took place in Athens, Greece from August 25th to 29th.

Our team has joined the conference in order to present the work of EU-HIP. Attendees at the knowledge transfer workshop "Towards interoperability with HERA's IT platform" had the chance to expand their knowledge about EU-HIP, HERA and ATHINA. The results of our landscape analysis and the common framework have been presented as well.

EU-HIP at MIE!

MAIN OBJECTIVES

Identification of the root causes of medicines shortages.

Identification and promotion of best practices in monitoring, reporting and managing medicines shortages.

Definition of a common dataset proposal for the notification and management of medicines shortages.

Reduction of shortages via preventive strategies.

Meet the project CHESSMEN

Just like the previous volumes, in this one we want to introduce you to another project co-funded by the European Union which is connected to the work of EU-HIP and could be interesting for you to follow. This time we are presenting to you the joint action CHESSMEN.

CHESSMEN (Coordination and Harmonisation of the Existing Systems against Shortages of Medicines - European Network) aims to support European Member States to provide a harmonized response to mitigate medicines shortages and to contribute to an appropriate and timely availability of medicinal products.

The project has officially started on January 16th 2023 and will be running for 3 years, bringing together a total of 22 countries participating as beneficiaries (21 EU Member States and 1 EEA country) and 5 entities participating as affiliated entities, under the coordination of AIFA - The Italian Medicines Agency (Agenzia Italiana del Farmaco), supported by the Italian National Blood and Transplant Centers (ISS-CNS/CNT).

In order to learn more visit their [official website!](#)

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